

Re-storying the Victory Square in Riga (ReVi) (Izp-2023/1-0237)

Version 0

Description

1. A representative sociological survey of the Latvian population, which will determine attitudes towards Victory Square in Riga and dismantling Soviet monument.
2. Online thematic questionnaires that will be addressed to specific target audiences so as to determine the views of various groups in society about the area of Victory Square. The plan is also to survey people who live in the neighbourhood of Victory Square so as to gain data about any sense of belonging to the neighbourhood, as well as to determine the role that it has about Victory Square. There are also plans for an online survey of young people to find out what they think about events that should be organised at the square.
3. Qualitative interviews will be another way of extracting data. The plan is to organise group interviews with people who are involved in maintaining and restructuring Victory Square. There will also be a survey of employees of companies and institutions in the area. The plan is to conduct separate interviews with various types of people such as those which use Victory Square for walks and sports, as well as those who live near to the site, as well as people in other regions of Riga. This will make it possible to determine how proximity to Victory Square influences attitudes about the place. There will be monitoring of what happens on May 9 so as to interview people who are still prepared to use the place so as to celebrate the Soviet victory of WWII. There will also be interviews with officials at the Riga City Council, as well as with experts related to history and memorial culture.
4. Data extracted by conducting participant and nonparticipant observations. Researchers will regularly visit Victory Square and make observations. They will take part in events at Victory Square such as clean-up sessions, sports events and performances. If possible, people who are encountered at the square will be interviewed, and the researchers will merge this with their overall work - working together, taking trips, caging and walking.
5. Photo and video collection. It will include photos and videos taken by researchers throughout the project

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Re-storying the Victory
Square in Riga (ReVi)

Researchers

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Ardava-Āboliņa, Marita Zītmāne

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Re-storying the Victory Square in Riga \(ReVi\) \(Izp-2023/1-0237\)](#)

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Researchers:

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Organizations:
University of Latvia

Contact: Vita Zelče

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Re-storying the Victory Square in Riga (ReVi)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2028-01-01

4. Templates

Descriptions

Representative sociological survey of the Latvian population about attitudes towards Victory Square and dismantling Soviet monument in Riga

The sociological survey will be commissioned by a sociological research company. Some 1,400 respondents from the age of 16 will be surveyed. According to data from the Central Statistical Board, a representative cohort of residents will mean that 5.3% of respondents will be aged 16–20, 16.5% will be aged 21–31, 24.3% will be 32–46, 23.7% will be 47–60, 20.6% will be 61–76, and 9.7% will be 77 years old or older. The plan is to rely on telephone interviews (CATI) with survey participants who are recruited in advance. This will ensure a cost-effective and methodologically appropriate data extraction method, reaching both economically active and economically inactive residents. The plan is that each interview will last for about 10 minutes. The survey focuses on attitudes toward “The monument of Soviet Latvian and Riga liberation from Fascist liberators” and its dismantling, as well as to the changes in Victory Square. These data will be of use when characterising trends

related to people's attitudes.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The survey data will be used in scientific publications and recommendations for state and local government institutions, as well as NGOs.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

html

1.1.4 Expected size of the data - give expected size and choose unit of measurement

Number

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

OpenAPC Global Initiative

id: null, Type: doi

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPSS

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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